

INCORPORATING GLOBAL ISSUES INTO TEACHING ESP FOR POLITICAL SCIENCE AND INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS STUDENTS

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Abstract. Global issues have become a contemporary focus in language teaching. Incorporating these topics into English teaching offers a unique opportunity to encourage worldwide awareness and critical thinking among students studying international relations and political science. Teachers can motivate students to engage with SDG global issues such as poverty, environmental sustainability, water scarcity, and quality education while improving their language skills. This paper reviewed how English teachers can approach the integration of global issues effectively.

Keywords: sustainable development goals, water scarcity, authentic vocabulary, assessments, global issues, environmental protection, human rights, poverty.

Teaching English requires different methods and new techniques in teaching ESP, significant experiences, and great efforts, and it also relies on the specific needs of the students. Teachers hold a vital and active role in teaching and learning regardless of the curriculum's value. Alan Maley (2017) noted, “Many professional teachers believe language teachers are more than just teachers of language. Through

what they teach, and their attitudes and practices, they have an enduring influence on their students' future attitudes and personalities”.

In September 2015, world leaders adopted a set of 17 United Nations Sustainable Development Goals with 169 targets. The SDGs provide a plan for addressing global challenges and can serve as engaging topics that go beyond standard grammar and vocabulary. Integrating SDG themes into English lessons can give International Relations students who learn diplomacy, political science, and social problems a purpose for learning while encouraging empathy and curiosity about the world. Moreover, English classes with International relations students offer a natural platform for discussing SDGs since they inherently involve language that supports debate, discussion, and conferences.

The integration of Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) into education has gained attention from scholars and educators who see it as a pathway to fostering global citizenship, environmental awareness, and social responsibility. Using practical activities for Integrating SDGs will enhance students' reading and listening comprehension. Teachers can use articles from authentic materials, real-life stories, or podcasts related to SDG topics to build students' reading and listening skills. For example, students can read a newspaper article on renewable energy advancements and discuss the impact of clean energy on communities. Furthermore, students can create poster presentations on the topic of poverty with possible solutions and proposals. The advantage of this approach is to engage students in visual and auditory learning, providing an engaging experience that complements traditional listening exercises (Prichard and Ferreira, 2014).

When teachers integrate communication tasks, collaborative work, or project work related to global issues, it enhances learners' active participation and critical thinking skills, rather than being passive recipients of information.

Tilbury highlights, that aligning education with the SDGs helps students to develop competencies such as critical thinking, collaboration, and systemic thinking, which are essential for addressing global challenges (Tilbury, 2011).

Moreover, it is very pivotal to combine the SDG topic of “Water Scarcity” and theme from the syllabi about “Water diplomacy”. As students of the International Relations of the UWED are future diplomats, it will be very significant for them to make decisions on very crucial problems of the global world and prepare them for their future careers. Mochizuki and Fadeeva argue that integrating SDGs into education helps develop students' ability to think and act sustainably, preparing them to address real-world sustainability issues effectively (Mochizuki and Fadeeva, 2010).

Additionally, encouraging debate on these topics, such as the impacts of climate change or water scarcity, builds students' critical thinking and speaking skills. Assigning roles or viewpoints helps students express ideas fluently and practice persuasive language, which is an essential skill in English proficiency

SDG themes offer an authentic context to introduce vocabulary and grammar. Discussing the second goal “Zero Hunger”, for instance, provides terms like "food security", "nutrition", and "sustainability." Teachers can create exercises, where students use these terms in sentences or paragraphs, reinforcing grammatical structures. UNESCO(2017), in its report, “Education for Sustainable Development Goals: Learning Objectives”, outlines the importance of incorporating SDG-related topics into curricula across all educational levels. The report provides a framework for how educators can teach students about each SDG, aiming to develop the skills, values, and attitudes necessary to contribute to a sustainable future. UNESCO emphasizes that education systems play a crucial role in achieving the SDGs by empowering students to become proactive global citizens (UNESCO, 2017). Integrating the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals into teaching

diplomatic vocabulary in English presents a meaningful way to enhance both language proficiency and global awareness. Diplomatic language skills require precision, tact, and a deep understanding of international issues—all of which align well with the SDG framework. By using SDG topics, English language teachers can develop students' diplomatic vocabulary while fostering a sense of responsibility toward global issues such as peace, environmental protection, and human rights.

Here is a procedure based on a lesson and how to adapt it for the learners.

1. Group students into small teams and instruct them to identify and list the five most significant challenges facing humanity.

2. Introduce the Sustainable Development Goals to the class by displaying and explaining the global goals poster. Then, ask learners to compare their lists with the 17 SDGs.

3. Organize learners into larger groups and have them imagine they are the General Assembly members. Assign each group one Sustainable Development Goal to explore and provide them with suitable authentic resources, such as articles or engaging materials. Ask them to read and learn about their assigned goal, then prepare proposals.

4. Invite each representative from the General Assembly to present their proposals.

5. Finally, hold a class vote for the most important SDG and proposal. Each student writes their top three SDGs on a slip of paper. Afterward, collect all the slips and tally the votes. Once the votes are counted, announce the class's top three SDGs based on the results.

It is important to point out that understanding the connection between SDGs and teaching diplomatic language, which addresses complex global challenges, requires cooperative, respectful, and thoughtful communication. Teaching English

vocabulary associated with diplomacy through SDG-related discussions provides a relevant context for students to learn the art of negotiation, agreement, and persuasive speech. Using SDG themes allows students to practice expressing opinions, negotiating agreements, and discussing sensitive topics, all while applying diplomatic vocabulary and language structures.

Furthermore, researchers highlight students' feedback on incorporating Sustainable Development Goals into their English language and literature classes. It emphasizes how this integration empowers students to actively engage in addressing global challenges, showcasing their involvement in classroom discussions and practical actions within their homes and communities. Students share that this approach enhances the relevance of their lessons, linking international relations to real-world issues while fostering critical thinking and problem-solving skills.

Evaluating students on their understanding of both language and SDG topics encourages a well-rounded approach. Assessments can focus on language accuracy, vocabulary use, and the ability to articulate thoughts on complex issues. Reflection exercises, where students consider what they have learned about the SDGs and how they feel about these global issues, deepen their understanding and personal engagement with the topics.

Combining SDGs into English for Specific Purposes classroom, especially for International Relations students, not only strengthens English language learning but also provides students with the knowledge, that is essential for future diplomats. This approach encourages learners to think critically about the world and how they can contribute positively to it. Participating in the debates, role-plays, and project works related to global problems enables students to address critical global challenges, such as climate change, poverty, and water scarcity. Sekerova noted, that incorporating role-playing and movement-based activities into foreign language

lessons enhances students' interest in both the class and the language-learning process (Sekerova, 2022).

Furthermore, by using authentic materials and emphasizing reflection, teachers motivate students to connect language learning with real-world challenges, making lessons relevant and impactful. This method promotes active engagement, empathy, and a sense of responsibility, turning students into proactive global citizens equipped with the skills to make informed decisions in their future roles.

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